

Uncoded optimal binary communication for sources with memory using the Burrows Wheeler Transform

Pedro M. Crespo, Estíbaliz Loyo, Javier Del Ser*

Department of Electronics and Communications, CEIT and TECNUN (University of Navarra), Paseo de Manuel Lardizabal 15, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastian, Spain

Received 16 January 2007; accepted 17 August 2007

Abstract

Given an AWGN channel, we look at the problem of designing an optimal binary uncoded communication system for transmitting blocks of binary symbols generated by a stationary source with memory modelled by a Markov chain (MC) or a hidden Markov model (HMM). The goal is to minimize the average SNR required for a given block error rate. The particular case where the binary source is memoryless with nonuniform symbol probabilities has been studied by Korn et al. [Optimal binary communication with nonequal probabilities. *IEEE Trans Commun* 2003;51:1435–8] [1] by optimally allocating the energies of the transmitted signals. In this paper we generalize the previous work to include the important case of sources with memory. The proposed system integrates the block sorting Burrows Wheeler Transform (BWT, [Burrows M, Wheeler D. A block sorting lossless data compression algorithm. Research report 124. Digital Systems Center, 1994]) [2] with an optimal energy allocation scheme based on the first order probabilities of the transformed symbols. Analytical expressions are derived for the energy gain obtained with the proposed system when compared either with the optimal blockwise MAP receiver or with a standard source coded system consisting of an optimal source encoder followed by an optimal uncoded binary communication system, i.e. by a symbol-by-symbol MAP detector.

© 2007 Elsevier GmbH. All rights reserved.

Keywords: Optimal communication; Markov models; Burrows Wheeler Transform

1. Introduction

One of the earliest goals of communication theory was to design and analyze the optimal binary communication receiver for the simplest AWGN channel. It is well known that, for this kind of channel, the bit error probability P_e is a monotonically decreasing function of the euclidian distance d between the two points of the binary signal constellation. Concretely, the expression for P_e is given by

(MAP receiver [3])

$$P_e = pQ\left(\frac{d}{2\sigma} - \frac{\sigma \ln\left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right)}{d}\right) + (1-p)Q\left(\frac{d}{2\sigma} + \frac{\sigma \ln\left(\frac{1-p}{p}\right)}{d}\right), \quad (1)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of the AWGN noise, $Q(\cdot)$ is the standard Q -function, and $(p, 1-p)$ denotes the probability distribution of the binary symbols (without loss of

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +34 943 212 800; fax: +34 943 213 076.

E-mail addresses: pcrespo@ceit.es (P.M. Crespo), eloyo@ceit.es (E. Loyo), jdelsers@ceit.es (J.D. Ser).

generality we assume $p \leq 0.5$). The distance d is a function of the energies E_0 and E_1 assigned by the digital modulator to the continuous time signals representing the zeros and ones, respectively. Assuming a stationary binary information source with symbol probabilities $p_0 = p$ and $p_1 = 1 - p$, the average energy at the input of the channel is $E = p_0 E_0 + p_1 E_1$.

Surprisingly, the interesting problem of minimizing P_e given an average energy E and an arbitrary p by finding the optimal values of E_0 and E_1 was overlooked for a long time until recently. The authors in Ref. [1] were the first to tackle this problem for the case of coherent and non-coherent receivers, and with arbitrary correlation between the signals. In [4] for the coherent case, a more general and straightforward solution is given to the problem first posed in [1]. Following [1,4] let us consider two arbitrary signals $\psi_i(t)$, $i \in \{0, 1\}$ of unitary energy, and form signals $s_0(t) = \sqrt{E_0} \psi_0(t)$ and $s_1(t) = \sqrt{E_1} \psi_1(t)$, where $\sqrt{E_0}$ and $\sqrt{E_1}$ are real coefficients defining the energy of the corresponding signals. The goal of the aforementioned papers was then to maximize the square of the euclidian distance d^2 between $s_0(t)$ and $s_1(t)$, that is,

$$d^2 = \int [s_0(t) - s_1(t)]^2 dt = E_0 + E_1 - 2\sqrt{E_0 E_1} \gamma \quad (2)$$

under the average energy constraint $pE_0 + (1-p)E_1 = E$. In the above expression $\gamma = \int \psi_0(t) \psi_1(t) dt$ is the correlation between the signals. As shown in [4], by defining the new variables $x = \sqrt{pE_0/E}$ and $y = \sqrt{(1-p)E_1/E}$, expression (2) can be rewritten as a quadratic form $d^2/E = (x, y) \mathbf{A} (x, y)^T$, and the corresponding constraint as $x^2 + y^2 = 1$. The entries of the 2×2 symmetric matrix $\mathbf{A}$ are $a_{11} = 1/p$, $a_{12} = -\gamma/\sqrt{p(1-p)}$ and $a_{22} = 1/(1-p)$. Therefore, maximizing d^2 for a given E and p is equivalent to finding the x and y that maximize $(x, y) \mathbf{A} (x, y)^T$. This reduces to finding the eigenvector of the greatest eigenvalue $\lambda_{\max}$ of the matrix $\mathbf{A}$. Thus, the optimal $d_{\max}^2$ is obtained as

$$d_{\max}^2(p, \gamma, E) = \lambda_{\max} E = \frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - 4p(1-p)(1-\gamma^2)}}{2p(1-p)} E \quad (3)$$

and the ratio of components as $y/x = a_{12}/(\lambda_{\max} - a_{22})$, which yields the optimal energies

$$E_0 = \frac{E}{p \left(1 + \frac{a_{12}^2}{(\lambda_{\max} - a_{22})^2} \right)}, \quad E_1 = \frac{E - pE_0}{1-p} \quad (4)$$

The term d/σ in expression (1) is given by

$$\frac{d}{\sigma} = \sqrt{\frac{E}{\sigma^2 a(\gamma, p)}} = \sqrt{\frac{\text{SNR}}{a(\gamma, p)}}, \quad (5)$$

with

$$a(\gamma, p) \triangleq \frac{E}{d_{\max}^2(p, \gamma, E)}, \quad 0 \leq p \leq 0.5 \quad (6)$$

and $\text{SNR} \triangleq E/\sigma^2$ denoting the signal to noise ratio.¹

Given $0 < p \leq 0.5$, we will refer to the above scheme of optimal energy allocation and symbol-by-symbol MAP detection, as the fixed optimal allocation (FOA) system, designed for probability p . Notice from expression (3) that the performance of the FOA communication system versus γ depends on $|\gamma|$ and therefore, it is sufficient to consider γ only in the range $\gamma \in [-1, 0]$.

In this paper, we focus on a more general problem by considering stationary binary sources with memory modelled as a Markov chain (MC) or hidden Markov model (HMM). It is well known that for sources with memory, the parameter that defines the statistical properties of a source S concerning compression is its entropy rate $\mathcal{H}(S)$ rather than its single letter entropy $H(U)$ which, for a source with memory, satisfies $H(U) > \mathcal{H}(S)$. Notice that, if a FOA scheme is directly applied to a source with memory, its performance will be restricted by the first-order probability (i.e., the marginal symbol distribution) of the source or, equivalently, by the probability p that yields the single letter entropy $h(p) = H(U)$, where $h(\cdot)$ denotes the standard binary entropy function.²

The conventional way to tackle the problem of transmitting information generated by sources with memory through an AWGN channel is to use a blockwise MAP detector at the receiver, even if channel coding is not used at the transmitter (in this paper we are not considering channel coding). From the previous discussion, and assuming binary transmission, the performance of this conventional system can be further improved by allocating the energies of the binary constellation in an optimal way, that is by using the FOA scheme designed for probability p , with $H(U) = h(p)$. We will refer to this system as *blockwise* FOA-MAP.

Another available option would be to use an ideal source coding and a symbol-by-symbol MAP detector at the receiver. Observe that in this case since the first order probabilities of the binary symbols at the output of the source encoder are i.i.d. and equiprobable, the optimal allocation of energy coincides with the standard equal energy constellation. Although the MAP detector becomes simpler than in the previous case, the design of an ideal source decoder is not straightforward, and will depend on the statistics of the source considered.

The communication scheme proposed in this paper follows a completely different approach. The main idea

¹ Observe that for antipodal signaling ($\gamma = -1$) E gives the energy per one dimension while in all the other cases E is the energy per two dimensions.

² $h(p) \triangleq -p \log_2 p - (1-p) \log_2 (1-p)$.

behind the scheme is to use a standard reversible transformation of the source symbols inside blocks of length K . In particular, the transformation used is the block sorting Burrows Wheeler Transform (BWT). From the properties of this transform, the optimal receiver reduces to a symbol-by-symbol MAP detector. Furthermore, since the transformed symbols inside a block are grouped into piecewise i.i.d intervals (consequently stationarity is lost inside a block), the optimal FOA can now be applied in each of these intervals or equivalently, optimal energy allocation in a symbol-by-symbol basis is now possible.

The paper derives closed-form expressions for the performance of the proposed scheme and shows that for any source with memory, the SNR required by the proposed system, for any target error probability P_e (under standard operational conditions, to be defined later), is

- lower bounded by the SNR required by a FOA system if the actual source with memory were to be replaced by a fictitious DMS source with single letter entropy equal to the entropy rate of the actual source, and
- upper bounded by the SNR required by an optimal blockwise FOA-MAP receiver with an optimal energy constellation designed for the given source. It is important to mention that this upper bound is never reached in the case of binary modulations other than orthogonal (i.e., for any modulations with $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$, such as BPSK). In other words, when $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$ our proposed system always outperforms the optimal blockwise FOA-MAP receiver.

In addition, simple conditions on the statistics of the source are given to assess how close the SNR of the proposed system is to the above lower bound. Finally, the proposed system is also compared with the aforementioned standard source coded system.

The BWT has been widely analyzed [5–7] and employed for the general problem of data compression [8,9]. More recent contributions have focused on the applicability of the BWT to coded transmission of Markov sources through AWGN channels via LDPC [10] and non-systematic Turbo codes [11]. None of the schemes in these two references are based on combining the BWT with the modulator. The authors in [12] propose a joint scheme comprising the BWT, a turbo code and a controlled BPSK modulator. The present paper focuses on the uncoded case, an arrangement not previously considered in the published literature.

The remainder of the paper is outlined as follows. In Section 2 we describe the proposed system formed by the combination of the BWT and an optimal energy allocation scheme. The corresponding energy gain of the system is also derived and bounded. Section 3 provides some examples of memory sources and shows the performance of the proposed system using the analytical expressions of Section 2 and corroborated by Montecarlo simulations. Finally, some concluding remarks are given in Section 4.

2. Proposed system

We consider the transmission of the information $\{U_k\}_{k=1}^{\infty}$ generated by a stationary ergodic binary source S with memory over an AWGN channel. It is assumed that the source S follows either a MC or a HMM. Its entropy rate $\mathcal{H}(S)$ is defined as

$$\mathcal{H}(S) \triangleq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} H(U_1, \dots, U_n) < H(U), \quad (7)$$

where $H(U)$ is its aforementioned single letter entropy. As already stated in the introduction, if the previous optimal energy allocation approach is applied directly to the source S , its performance will be limited by the first-order probability of the source $(P_U(0), P_U(1)) = (p_m, 1 - p_m)$, with $p_m \leq 0.5$ being the unique solution to $h(p_m) = H(U)$ (the subindex m will stand in the sequel for *memoryless*).

The proposed system is shown in Fig. 1. As already mentioned in the introduction, the main idea is to transform the original memory source S into a piecewise memoryless source, and then use the optimal energy allocation scheme (FOA) in each piecewise interval. This is possible by applying the block sorting BWT to blocks of K source symbols. Let $\mathbf{T} = \{T_k\}_{k=1}^K$ denote the output sequence of the BWT.³ For sources modelled by Markov chains, it was shown in [7] that the output distribution $P_{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{t})$ of the random sequence $\mathbf{T}$ is approximately memoryless and piecewise stationary, in the sense that the normalized divergence between the output distribution and a memoryless and piecewise stationary distribution is small. In other words, there exists a probability distribution $Q_{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{t})$ that can be expressed as

$$Q_{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{t}) = \prod_{i=1}^M \prod_{k=C_{i-1}}^{C_i-1} Q_i(t_k) \quad (8)$$

such that the normalized divergence between both distributions can be made arbitrarily small for sufficiently large K , i.e.

$$\frac{1}{K} D(Q_{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{t}) \| P_{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{t})) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{when } K \rightarrow \infty. \quad (9)$$

In expression (8), $C_0 = 1$ and M denotes the number of piecewise i.i.d. intervals $l_i = [C_{i-1}, C_i)$ of length $|l_i|$ with first-order probability distribution function

$$Q_i(t_k) \triangleq \begin{cases} p_i & \text{if } t_k = 0, \\ 1 - p_i & \text{if } t_k = 1, \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$\forall k \in l_i, i = 1, \dots, M$. Furthermore, for large K the ratios $|l_i|/K$ do not depend on the input block length K , and M is the number of states in the Markov chain that describes the source. In case of dealing with a finite state HMM source, the source can be thought to be a MC with an infinite number

³ Additionally the BWT generates an index $J \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ to avoid edge ambiguities [2]. This issue is discussed in Section 3.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed system.

of states or, for all practical purposes, by a finite state MC having a number of states larger than the number of states in the original HMM.

Definition 1. Given a source S , we define its zero (one) probability profile as $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k) \triangleq P_{T_k}(t_k = 0)$ ($\mathcal{P}_S^1(k) \triangleq P_{T_k}(t_k = 1)$), $k = 1, \dots, K$, where $P_{T_k}(t_k)$ is the marginal probability distribution of $P_{\mathbf{T}}(\mathbf{t})$ at time k .

Definition 2. The folded probability profile of a source, $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$, is defined as

$$\mathcal{P}_S(k) \triangleq \min[\mathcal{P}_S^0(k), \mathcal{P}_S^1(k)], \quad (11)$$

where $k = 1, \dots, K$.

Fig. 3 plots $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$ for some of the sources considered in Section 3. Notice that $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$ can take values in the interval $\mathcal{P}_S(k) \in [0, 0.5]$; however, for a large number of sources of interest, $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$ will typically lie in the interval $[0.05, 0.5]$.

Proposition 1. Let $\{U_k\}_{k=1}^\infty$ be the output of an ergodic binary source S with joint probability distribution $P_{\mathbf{U}}(\mathbf{u})$, single letter entropy $H(U)$ and entropy rate $\mathcal{H}(S)$. Let $\mathbf{U} = \{U_k\}_{k=1}^K$ be the input to the BWT and $\mathbf{T} = \{T_k\}_{k=1}^K$ its corresponding output. Then in the limit when K grows to infinity, $H(U)$ and $\mathcal{H}(S)$ are given by

- $H(U) = h(\langle \mathcal{P}_S^0 \rangle) = h(\langle \mathcal{P}_S^1 \rangle) = h(p_m)$, where

$$\langle \mathcal{P}_S^i \rangle \triangleq \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathcal{P}_S^i(k), \quad i \in \{0, 1\} \quad (12)$$

and

$$p_m = \min[\langle \mathcal{P}_S^0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{P}_S^1 \rangle]. \quad (13)$$

- $\mathcal{H}(S) = \langle h(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K h(\mathcal{P}_S(k))$.

Proof. By the ergodicity of the source, the sequence of random variables $\{1/K \sum_{k=1}^K U_k\}_{K=1}^\infty$ converges almost everywhere (a.e.) to $\mathbb{E}(U_k) = P_U(1)$, where $\mathbb{E}(\cdot)$ denotes

expectation. That is,

$$P_U(1) = 1 - P_U(0) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K U_k \quad (\text{a.e.}) \quad (14)$$

On the other hand, the BWT is a block sorting transformation; thereby the number of ones in an input and an output block is the same. Consequently, $P_U(u)$ can also be obtained as

$$P_U(1) = 1 - P_U(0) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K T_k \quad (\text{a.e.}) \quad (15)$$

Using the fact that $0 \leq 1/K \sum_{k=1}^K T_k \leq 1 \forall K$ and consequently $\{1/K \sum_{k=1}^K T_k\}_{K=1}^\infty$ is a sequence of positive bounded random variables, we can apply the Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem [13] to expression (15) to show that

$$\begin{aligned} P_U(1) &= \mathbb{E}(P_U(1)) = \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbb{E}(T_k) \\ &= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \mathcal{P}_S^1(k) \quad (\text{a.e.}) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Now, the first part of the proposition is proven by the definition of $H(U) \triangleq h(P_U(1))$ and the symmetry of the entropy function $h(\cdot)$. The second part follows from the reversibility of the BWT and the fact that, for large K , the output symbols T_k are independent. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{H}(S) &\triangleq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} H(U_1, \dots, U_K) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} H(T_1, \dots, T_K) \\ &= \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K H(T_k), \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

with $H(T_k) \triangleq h(P_{T_k}(0)) = h(\mathcal{P}_S^0(k))$. Again by the symmetry property of the entropy function we get

$$\mathcal{H}(S) = \langle h(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle. \quad \square \quad (18)$$

Corollary 1. Let $\mathcal{H}(S) < H(U)$, and $p_{\text{er}} \leq 0.5$ and $p_m \leq 0.5$ be the unique solutions to $h(p_{\text{er}}) = \mathcal{H}(S)$ and $h(p_m) = H(U)$. Then

$$p_m \geq \langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle \geq p_{\text{er}}. \quad (19)$$

Furthermore, in the above expression equalities cannot simultaneously hold, and $\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle = p_{\text{er}}$ if and only if $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = p_{\text{er}} \forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$.

Proof. From Proposition 1 and the fact that $h(p)$ is a monotonically increasing strictly concave function ($0 \leq p \leq 0.5$),

we have by the Jensen’s inequality [14] that

$$h(p_{\text{er}}) = \mathcal{H}(S) = \langle h(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle \leq h(\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle) \Rightarrow p_{\text{er}} \leq \langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle.$$

On the other hand, by definition, $\mathcal{P}_S(k) \leq \mathcal{P}_S^i(k) \forall k$ and $i \in \{0, 1\}$. Therefore,

$$\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle \leq \min[\langle \mathcal{P}_S^0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{P}_S^1 \rangle] = p_m \tag{20}$$

and we conclude that

$$p_m \geq \langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle \geq p_{\text{er}}. \tag{21}$$

The last statement now follows immediately by contradiction. Suppose that the condition does not hold, then $p_m = p_{\text{er}}$, implying that $H(U) = \mathcal{H}(S)$. This contradicts the initial hypothesis that $H(U) > \mathcal{H}(S)$.

Finally, notice that since the entropy function $h(p)$ is strictly concave, equality will hold in $\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle \geq p_{\text{er}}$ if and only if the folded probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$ is a constant function of k taking value p_{er} . Therefore, $\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle > p_{\text{er}}$ whenever $\mathcal{P}_S(k) \neq p_{\text{er}}$. $\square$

Let us go back to the system of Fig. 1. Assume that both transmitter and receiver know the zero probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$ (as explained in Section 3, $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$ can be estimated online at the transmitter and receiver side). The modulator uses this information to allocate the symbol energies. The allocation scheme is similar to the one explained in the introduction (FOA); however, in this case the allocation of energy is time variant depending on the zero probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$ at each time instant $k = 1, \dots, K$. Similarly, the symbol-by-symbol MAP detector at the receiver, will adjust its decision threshold in accordance with $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$. It should be mentioned, the otherwise obvious statement, that the proposed and the FOA systems coincide when are designed for memoryless sources (DMS).

Next we analyze the required SNR for a given block error rate (BLER), and compute the energy gains when compared either with the blockwise FOA-MAP system or with a standard system using an optimal source encoder. Observe that the probability of receiving a block in error at the output of the inverse BWT equals the probability that the corresponding input block presents at least one error. Therefore, if K is the length of the block, the BLER is given by

$$\text{BLER} = 1 - (1 - P_e)^K, \tag{22}$$

where P_e is the probability that a binary symbol $\hat{l}_k$ ($k = 1, \dots, K$) at the output of the detector is in error. In the following derivations we will consider P_e instead of BLER. However, notice that P_e is several orders of magnitude lower than BLER. For example, for a $\text{BLER} \leq 10^{-4}$ and $K = 5000$, the required P_e should be approximately upper bounded by 10^{-8} . Therefore, it is sound to say that for reliable communications one should achieve $P_e \in (0, 10^{-8}]$. Based on this consideration and on the previous remark regarding the range of $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$, we define by *standard operational*

conditions (SOC) the following two conditions:

$$P_e \in (0, 10^{-8}] \text{ and } \mathcal{P}_S \in [0.05, 0.5]. \tag{23}$$

The purpose of next propositions is to derive expressions of the energy gain of the proposed system when compared to the previously mentioned conventional systems. To this end, and to be able to obtain closed-form expressions that do not depend on P_e^* , we need to simplify the error probability formula in expression (1). It can be checked that for SOC, a good approximation for this expression is

$$P_e \approx Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{SNR}}{4a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}} \right). \tag{24}$$

In other words under SOC, the performance of a MAP receiver is similar to that of a ML receiver. In the sequel, all derivations are based on expression (24) either because we are considering a ML receiver or because we are under SOC.

Proposition 2. *Let S be the source defined in Proposition 1, with a folded probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$, $k = 1, \dots, K$. Denote by $\{\text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)}\}_{k=1}^K$ the SNR allotted at each k , and*

$$\widehat{\text{SNR}} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)} \tag{25}$$

its average per BLOCK. Then, the optimal set of SNR values that minimize $\widehat{\text{SNR}}$ for a given P_e^ is given by*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)}(P_e^*) &= 4a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k)) \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} P_e^* \right) \right]^2 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

and

$$\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) = 4 \left\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} P_e^* \right) \right]^2 \right\rangle. \tag{27}$$

Proof. From expressions (8) and (9), the binary sequence of length K at the output of the BWT can be thought (only for didactic purposes) to be the concatenation of M subsequences of lengths $|l_i|$ ($i = 1, \dots, M$) generated by memoryless sources with first-order probability distributions $\{p_i\}_{i=1}^M$, with $p_i \triangleq \mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$, $\forall k \in l_i$. The optimum energy allocation in each i subsequence is given by the aforementioned FOA scheme, designed for the corresponding p_i . Define $\hat{p}_i = \min(p_i, 1 - p_i)$, i.e., $\hat{p}_i \triangleq \mathcal{P}_S(k)$, $\forall k \in l_i$. Let SNR_i be the associated signal to noise ratio, i.e., $\text{SNR}_i \triangleq \text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)}$, $\forall k \in l_i$.

We wish to find the optimal set of SNR values that minimizes the average $\widehat{\text{SNR}}$ for a given P_e^* . That is, we want to minimize

$$\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) = \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{|l_i|}{K} \text{SNR}_i = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K \text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)} \tag{28}$$

subject to constraint

$$\begin{aligned} P_e^* &= \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{|l_i|}{K} Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{SNR}_i}{4a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i)}} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)}}{4a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

This is a standard optimization problem that can be solved using Lagrange multipliers. The solution is obtained by equating to zero the derivatives, with respect to SNR_k , of the functional

$$J(\text{SNR}_i) \triangleq \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{|l_i|}{K} \text{SNR}_i + \xi \left(\sum_{i=1}^M \frac{|l_i|}{K} Q(v_i) \right), \quad (30)$$

where $v_i = \sqrt{\frac{\text{SNR}_i}{4a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i)}}$. That is,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial J}{\partial \text{SNR}_i} &= \frac{|l_i|}{K} + \xi \frac{|l_i|}{K} \frac{\partial Q(v_i)}{\partial \text{SNR}_i} \\ &= \frac{|l_i|}{K} + \xi \frac{|l_i|}{K} \frac{\partial Q(v_i)}{\partial v_i} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial \text{SNR}_i} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

For the range of values of P_e^* of interest ($v_i = Q^{-1}(P_e^*) > 5.6$), we can tightly approximate the Q-function as [3, Chapter 2.3]

$$Q(v_i) \cong \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}v_i} \exp\left(-\frac{v_i^2}{2}\right) \quad (32)$$

thus expression (31) reduces to

$$\frac{|l_i|}{K} - \xi \frac{|l_i|}{K} Q(v_i) \left(\frac{v_i^2 + 1}{v_i} \right) \frac{1}{2\sqrt{4a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i)\text{SNR}_i}} = 0.$$

Using the fact that $(v_i^2 + 1/v_i) \approx v_i$, it follows from the above equality that

$$Q(v_i) = \frac{8a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i)}{\xi}, \quad (33)$$

where the value of ξ is determined from the previous constraint, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} P_e^* &= \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{|l_i|}{K} Q(v_i) = \frac{8}{\xi} \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{|l_i|}{K} a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i) \\ &= \frac{8}{\xi} \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k)) = \frac{8}{\xi} a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

yielding

$$\xi = \frac{8a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)}{P_e^*}. \quad (35)$$

Therefore, from (33) the probability of error associated to subsequence i is

$$Q(v_i) = Q \left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{SNR}_i}{4a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i)}} \right) = \frac{a(\gamma, \hat{p}_i)}{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)} P_e^*. \quad (36)$$

This yields the set of values

$$\text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)} = 4a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k)) \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\mathcal{P}_S(k))}{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)} P_e^* \right) \right]^2,$$

where $k=1, \dots, K$. Since the $\text{SNR}_{\mathcal{P}_S(k)}$ are all positive, the Kuhn–Tucker conditions are verified and consequently this is the optimal set achieving the minimum $\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*)$. This minimum value is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) &= \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K 4a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k)) \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)} P_e^* \right) \right]^2 \\ &\triangleq 4 \left\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)}{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)} P_e^* \right) \right]^2 \right\rangle. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

It is shown in the appendix that under SOC expression (27) can be further approximated by

$$\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) = 4 \langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle [Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2. \quad (38)$$

The next definition paves the way to assess the performance gain of the proposed system when compared to the class of blockwise MAP receivers, with or without FOA.

Definition 3. Let S be the source defined in Proposition 1 with folded probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$, $k=1, \dots, K$. Given a probability of error P_e^* , we define by $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p, P_e^*)$ the energy gain of our proposed system when compared with a FOA system assuming that has been designed for a fictitious memoryless source having single letter entropy $h(p)$. That is,

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p, P_e^*) \triangleq \frac{\text{SNR}_p(P_e^*)}{\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*)}, \quad (39)$$

where $\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e)$ denotes the required SNR to achieve a P_e with the proposed system, whereas $\text{SNR}_p(P_e)$ gives the required SNR for a FOA system designed for a DMS source with symbol probability p .

There are four values of p with a clear operational meaning. These are $p=0.5$, $p=p_m$, $p=p_{er}$ and $p=\check{p}$, where $\check{p}$ is the solution of $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, \check{p}, P_e^*)=1$. When $p=0.5$ or $p=p_m$, expression (39) gives the energy gain obtained by the proposed system when compared to a blockwise MAP receiver either using an equal energy allocation modulator or a FOA energy allocation scheme designed for p_m , i.e., designed based on the first-order probability distribution of the source symbols.

To understand why $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p, P_e^*)$ with $p=0.5$ or $p=p_m$ gives the above energy gain, one has to realize that the performance of the blockwise MAP receiver is the same as the performance that would be obtained should the proposed system be designed for a fictitious DMS source with symbol probabilities p_m (instead of the actual source with memory and entropy per letter $h(p_m)$) and using this system

to transmit the information generated by the actual source. This is so because the BWT is a block sorting (reversible) transformation. Consequently, the Hamming weight of the input and output binary sequences, as well as their probability of generation, are the same. Therefore, for a fixed energy constellation, the performance of the following two systems should be the same:

1. Source → modulator → channel → blockwise MAP receiver.
2. Source → BWT → modulator → channel → blockwise MAP receiver.

Now, from the properties of the BWT (independence of the transformed symbols) the blockwise MAP detector in system 2 reduces to a symbol-by-symbol MAP detector. This in turn is nothing other than the situation considered, namely, the performance of the proposed system (or a FOA system) designed for a fictitious DMS source with symbol probabilities $p = 0.5$ or p_m .

Looking at the case when $p = p_{er}$, expression (39) compares the energy required by the proposed system with that of a FOA system designed for a fictitious DMS source with symbol probability distribution p_{er} , i.e., a DMS source having single letter entropy $\mathcal{H}(S)$. Finally, $p = \check{p}$ gives the probability distribution of a fictitious DMS source such that if a FOA system was used to transmit these symbols it would require the same energy as our proposed system.

The following proposition is a direct consequence of expression (38).

Proposition 3. *Let S be the source defined in Proposition 1. Then under SOC, the energy gain $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p, P_e^*)$ in Definition 3 does not depend on P_e^* , and is given by*

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p, P_e^*) = G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p) = \frac{a(\gamma, p)}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle}. \quad (40)$$

In particular, the energy gain with respect to a standard equal energy allocation scheme ($p = 0.5$) is given by

$$G_{eq}(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) = \frac{(1 - \gamma)^{-1}}{2\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle}. \quad (41)$$

The next proposition proves the claim stated earlier that for binary modulations other than orthogonal the proposed system always outperform the blockwise MAP receiver.

Proposition 4. *Let S be the source defined in Proposition 1 with single letter entropy $H(U)$, entropy rate $\mathcal{H}(S) < H(U)$, and folded probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$. Then, the energy gain $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p)$ in Proposition 3 verifies the following inequalities:*

- For $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$:

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) > G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, \check{p}) = 1 \geq G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}), \quad (42)$$

where p_m and p_{er} are the unique solutions to $h(p_m) = H(U)$, and $h(p_{er}) = \mathcal{H}(S)$, $p_m, p_{er} \leq 0.5$.

- For $\gamma = 0$:

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) \geq G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, \check{p}) = 1 \geq G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}), \quad (43)$$

with equality in $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) \geq G(\mathcal{P}_S, \check{p}) = 1$ if and only if the folded probability function $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$ is equal to either $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$ or $\mathcal{P}_S^1(k)$ for all k (i.e. when either $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k) \leq 0.5$ or $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k) \geq 0.5, \forall k$).

Proof. We begin by proving the second inequality, i.e., $1 \geq G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}), \forall \gamma \in [-1, 0]$. From Proposition 1

$$h(p_{er}) = \mathcal{H}(S) = \langle h(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle = \langle h(a^{-1}(\gamma, a(\mathcal{P}_S))) \rangle, \quad (44)$$

where $a^{-1}(\gamma, v)$, with $0 \leq v \leq \frac{1}{2(1-\gamma)}$, denotes the inverse function of $a(\gamma, p)$ with respect to p , that is, $a^{-1}(\gamma, a(\gamma, p)) = p$. By defining

$$V(\gamma, v) \triangleq h(a^{-1}(\gamma, v)), \quad 0 \leq v \leq \frac{1}{2(1-\gamma)}, \quad (45)$$

the above expression can be rewritten as

$$h(p_{er}) = \mathcal{H}(S) = \langle h(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle = \langle V(\gamma, a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)) \rangle. \quad (46)$$

For fixed $\gamma \in [-1, 0]$, it can be checked that the function $V(\gamma, v)$ is a monotonically increasing strictly concave function of v (its second derivative is always less than zero). Therefore, by the Jensen's inequality $h(p_{er})$ is upper bounded by $V(\gamma, \langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle)$. Applying first $h^{-1}(\cdot)$ and then $a(\cdot)$ to both sides of the above inequality yields the sought result (see expression (40))

$$a(\gamma, p_{er}) \leq \langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle \Rightarrow 1 \geq G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}), \quad (47)$$

with equality only if $a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k)) = a(\gamma, p_{er}), \forall k$ or, equivalently, if $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = p_{er}, \forall k$.

To finish the proposition we have to prove the first inequality, that is, $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) \geq 1$. To this end, one has to distinguish two cases: $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$ and $\gamma = 0$.

- For $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$: From Definition 2 and expression (13), it always holds that $p_m \geq \langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle$. Using the fact that for $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$, $a(\gamma, p)$ is a monotonically increasing strictly concave function of p (its second derivative is always less than zero) yields

$$\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle \leq a(\gamma, \langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle) \leq a(\gamma, p_m), \quad (48)$$

where the Jensen's inequality has again been used to obtain the first inequality, with equality only if $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = c$, i.e. a constant function of k . Its value follows from the fact that $\langle h(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle = h(p_{er})$ (Proposition 1), so $c = p_{er}$. Therefore we conclude that, if $\mathcal{P}_S(k) \neq p_{er}$, then

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) = \frac{a(\gamma, p_m)}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} > 1. \quad (49)$$

On the other hand, when $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = p_{er}$, it could happen that

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) = 1. \quad (50)$$

However, we have proved above that $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = p_{er}$ also implies $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}) = 1$, so if $G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) = 1$, it

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. Theoretical gains $G_c(\mathcal{P}_S(k), \gamma)$ for (a) orthogonal and (b) antipodal binary constellations and several values of the ratio $\tilde{p}/p_{er}$.

would yield

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) = G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}) \quad (51)$$

or that $p_m = p_{er}$, contradicting the fact that $H(U) > \mathcal{H}(S)$.

- For $\gamma=0$: In this case, $a(\gamma, p) = p$ and therefore, although $a(0, p)$ is monotonically increasing concave function, it is not anymore strictly concave (its second derivative is zero). Consequently, the inequalities in expression (48) reduce to

$$\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle \leq p_m. \quad (52)$$

Notice that equality in the above expression implies that

$$\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle = p_m = \min[\langle \mathcal{P}_S^0 \rangle, \langle \mathcal{P}_S^1 \rangle]. \quad (53)$$

Therefore equality in $a(\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle) \leq a(p_m)$ or, equivalently, in $G(\mathcal{P}_S, 0, p_m) \geq 1$, will happen if and only if the folded probability function $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$ is equal to either $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$ or $\mathcal{P}_S^1(k)$ for all k . This finishes the proposition. $\square$

We end this section by evaluating the energy gain of the proposed system when compared to a standard source coded system, that is, a transmission system consisting of an optimal source encoder followed by an optimal uncoded binary system.

Proposition 5. Let S be the source defined in Proposition 40 with entropy rate $\mathcal{H}(S) = h(p_{er})$ and folded probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S(k)$. The energy gain of the proposed system when compared to a standard source coded system is given by

$$G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) = \frac{(1-\gamma)^{-1} \mathcal{H}(S)}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} = G_{eq}(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) \mathcal{H}(S). \quad (54)$$

Proof. It is well known from the Source Coding Theorem [15] that an optimal binary source encoder generates equiprobable symbols with a reduction in transmission rate by a factor equal to the entropy rate of the source. This implies an increase of the energy of the coded symbols by a factor $1/\mathcal{H}(S)$. Therefore, given a target P_e^* , the SNR_c required for a scheme with optimal source encoding will be $\mathcal{H}(S)$ times the SNR_{eq} required by an uncoded equal energy

Table 1. Parameters for the selected models

Src	Model	$H(U)$	p_m	$\mathcal{H}(S)$	P_{er}
S_1	MC 2 states	0.81	0.25	0.58	0.139
S_2	MC 3 states	0.987	0.433	0.599	0.145
S_3	MC 4 states	0.807	0.247	0.371	0.071
S_4	HMM 2 states	0.815	0.251	0.624	0.156
S_5	HMM 3 states	0.996	0.463	0.793	0.24
S_6	HMM 4 states	0.996	0.463	0.723	0.2

allocation scheme. Therefore,

$$G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) \triangleq \frac{\text{SNR}_c}{\text{SNR}} = \frac{\text{SNR}_{\text{eq}} \mathcal{H}(S)}{\text{SNR}} = G_{\text{eq}}(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) \mathcal{H}(S), \quad (55)$$

where $G_{\text{eq}}(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma)$ is given by expression (41). $\square$

Notice that $G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma)$ can also be written as

$$G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) = \frac{(1 - \gamma)^{-1}}{2a(\gamma, \check{p})} h(p_{\text{er}}), \quad (56)$$

showing its dependence on the source parameters $\check{p}$ and p_{er} . Figs. 2a and 2b plot the energy gain $G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma)$ in the range $0.1 < \mathcal{H}(S) \leq 0.6$ and ratios $1 \leq \check{p}/p_{\text{er}} \leq 1.25$, for $\gamma = 0$ and -1 , respectively.

In the next section we corroborate by simulation the above theoretical gains assuming that both transmitter and receiver estimate on line the zero probability profile $\mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$.

3. Examples

In this section, we obtain the performance of the proposed system using the analytical expressions previously derived and compare the results with the corresponding computer simulation. Six sources have been selected, three modelled by MC's and the remaining three by HMM's. Table 1 shows the parameters of these sources.

The Monte Carlo simulation uses blocks of $K = 5000$ binary source symbols, and starts with a training period for the initial estimation of the zero probability profile at the transmitter and receiver side. During this training period the allocation of energies in the modulator is the same for both signals (i.e., $E_0 = E_1$) and the SNR is sufficiently high to achieve a probability of error less than 10^{-8} at the output of the optimal detector. The zero probability profile is estimated using frequency of occurrence as

$$\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(k) \triangleq \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbb{1}(t_k(n) = 0). \quad (57)$$

At the transmitter side, $t_k(n)$ is the output symbol of the BWT at position $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ and block $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, whereas $\mathbb{1}(t_k(n) = 0)$ is the indication function taking value 1 when $t_k(n) = 0$ and 0 otherwise. At the receiver side, $t_k(n)$ is $\hat{t}_k(n)$, i.e., the output of the optimum detector (see Fig. 1). Notice that at low P_e , the estimated $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(k)$ at the receiver and transmitter side will be practically the same. In the simulation, the initial estimation of $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(k)$ uses $N = 10^4$. After this training period, the transmitter and receiver switches to normal operation. That is, the allocation of energies is based on the estimated $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(k)$ and uses the following simplification of expression (26) (good approximation under SOC),

$$E(k) = 4a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))\alpha, \quad (58)$$

Fig. 3. Estimated profiles $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(k)$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S(k)$ for sources (a) S_2 (b) S_4 (c) S_5 .

where α controls the overall SNR. The splitting of $E(k)$ between $E_0(k)$ and $E_1(k)$ is set by expressions (4). On the other hand, the receiver has been implemented as a MAP

Table 2. Theoretical gains for the selected models in dB

Gain	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_4	S_5	S_6
$\gamma = -1$						
$G_{\text{eq}}(P_S, \gamma)$	3.10	2.778	5.40	2.34	1.344	1.866
$G(P_S, \gamma, p_m)$	1.85	2.703	4.154	1.12	1.32	1.84
$G_c(P_S, \gamma)$	0.74	0.556	1.112	0.296	0.337	0.459
$G(P_S, \gamma, p_{\text{er}})$	-0.112	-0.268	-0.414	-0.445	-0.024	-0.062
$\tilde{p}/p_{\text{er}}$	1.12	1.21	1.31	1.61	1.09	1.10
$\gamma = 0$						
$G_{\text{eq}}(P_S, \gamma)$	5.08	4.543	7.397	2.975	2.814	3.532
$G(P_S, \gamma, p_m)$	2.07	3.936	4.349	0.011	2.482	3.188
$G_c(P_S, \gamma)$	2.71	2.322	3.081	0.932	1.807	2.126
$G(P_S, \gamma, p_{\text{er}})$	-0.496	-0.833	-1.141	-2.083	-0.373	-0.434
$\tilde{p}/p_{\text{er}}$	1.03	1.07	1.11	1.13	1.01	1.02

receiver based on $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(\ell)$. During this mode of operation, the number of blocks has been set to 10^6 and the zero error profile can be estimated on line.

At this point it must be mentioned that the index J (see footnote 3) required by the inverse BWT transform has to be sent together with every block of K symbols. This requires sending $\log_2 K$ additional bits. These bits should be received without any errors to allow the inverse BWT to properly recover the original source blocks. This could be achieved either by protecting the index bits with a high rate channel code (such as a BCH code) or by allocating higher energy to those bits. In any case, the penalty paid is negligible due to the small overhead incurred (in our case, $\log_2 K/K = 0.0025$). Therefore, in the presented simulation such an overhead has not been considered.

Fig. 3 plots the initial estimated profiles for sources S_2 , S_4 and S_5 . In the same figure the corresponding folded probability profiles $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(\ell)$ are also shown. Observe that source S_2 has been generated by a MC with three states, and this fact is clearly shown by the three piecewise intervals on its $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}_S^0(\ell)$. The other two sources S_4 and S_5 are HMM with 2 and 3 states, respectively. Notice, in contrast, that in these cases there is not a clear connection between the piecewise intervals and the number of states.

Table 2 shows the gains obtained using the analytical expressions (40), (41) and (54) and the corresponding initial estimated folded probability profiles for both $\gamma = -1$ and $\gamma = 0$. When the energy gains are computed based on the Montecarlo simulation the deviations with respect to Table 2 are less than 2% at a P_e of 10^{-8} . Should we have used a ML receiver instead of the MAP receiver the deviations would be negligible. These agreements imply that the block length K used is sufficiently large so that the probability of generating a nontypical block by the source is small. By a nontypical block it is meant a block that when transformed by the BWT, its likelihood of being drawn from a distribution given by the estimated average probability profile (57) is small.

From Table 2 observe that, for all the sources under consideration and $\gamma = -1$, significant gains (up to 4.154 dB for source S_3) are attained by utilizing the proposed BWT based system when compared to a standard blockwise FOA-MAP system. However, notice that this gain reduces to 0.011 dB for source S_4 and $\gamma = 0$. The reason being that, as shown in Fig. 3b and predicted in Proposition 4, $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = \mathcal{P}_S^0(k)$ for most k ; from expression (13), $\langle \mathcal{P}_S(k) \rangle = \langle \mathcal{P}_S^0(k) \rangle = p_m$ and, consequently,

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma = 0, p_m) = \frac{a(0, p_m)}{\langle a(0, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} = \frac{p_m}{\langle \mathcal{P}_S \rangle} \approx 1 \quad (0 \text{ dB}).$$

Finally, notice that in all the considered cases, the proposed system outperforms the standard arrangement of an ideal source encoder followed by an equal energy allocation modulator and symbol-by-symbol MAP detector. Also, the actual performance of the proposed system is close to that of a FOA system designed for a fictitious DMS source with single letter entropy equal to $\mathcal{H}(S) = h(p_{\text{er}})$.

4. Conclusions

We have proposed a binary communication system that integrates the block sorting BWT with an optimal energy allocation scheme based on the first order distribution of the transformed symbols. Under SOC conditions defined in expression (23), we have derived closed-form expressions for the performance of the proposed system. For sources where the entropy rate $\mathcal{H}(S) = h(p_{\text{er}})$ is smaller than their single letter entropy $H(U) = h(p_m)$, the following conclusions hold:

- The $\widehat{\text{SNR}}$ required for the proposed system is upper bounded by the SNR_{p_m} required by the optimal blockwise MAP receiver with an optimal energy allocation (FOA) designed for p_m (i.e., blockwise FOA-MAP

system). That is,

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) \geq 1. \tag{59}$$

In particular, for $\gamma \in [-1, 0)$ the proposed system always outperforms the blockwise FOA-MAP system ($G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_m) > 1$).

- The SNR required for the proposed system is lower bounded by the SNR_{per} required by a FOA system if the actual source with memory is replaced by a fictitious DMS source with single letter entropy equal to $\mathcal{H}(S) = h(p_{er})$, that is,

$$G(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma, p_{er}) \leq 1. \tag{60}$$

Equality holds if and only if $\mathcal{P}_S(k) = p_{er}, \forall k$.

- The energy gain of the proposed system when compared to a standard coded system consisting of an optimal binary source encoder followed by an optimum uncoded binary system is given by

$$G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) = \frac{(1 - \gamma)^{-1} \mathcal{H}(S)}{2\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} = G_{eq}(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma) \mathcal{H}(S). \tag{61}$$

This gain depends on the source parameters $\check{p}$ and p_{er} (see Fig. 2). Observe from Table 2 that for all the sources considered in Section 3, $G_c(\mathcal{P}_S, \gamma)$ is greater than 1 dB.

Acknowledgments

This work has been partially supported by the *Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia* of Spain under the Torres Quevedo program, as well as by the Basque Government Ministry of Industry under both TECMAR (IBA/PI2004-3) and INFOS-ETEC (S-PE06CE10) research projects.

Appendix A.

In this appendix we show that expression

$$\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) = 4 \left\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S)}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} P_e^* \right) \right]^2 \right\rangle \tag{A.1}$$

in Proposition 2 can be approximated under SOC by

$$\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) = 4\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle [Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2. \tag{A.2}$$

Let us identify $a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(j))$ as a discrete random variable $A(j)$ defined in the discrete probability space $\{\Omega, \mathcal{F}, Pr\}$ with $\Omega = \{1, \dots, K\}$, $\mathcal{F}$ the set of all subsets of Ω , and Pr the normalized counting measure, i.e., $Pr(\mathcal{B}) = |\mathcal{B}|/K, \forall \mathcal{B} \in \mathcal{F}$.

Proposition 1. Expression (A.1) can be approximated by expression (A.2) whenever

$$\frac{[Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2}{2} \gg \frac{\mathbb{E}(A^2) - (\mathbb{E}(A))^2}{(\mathbb{E}(A))^2} \triangleq \text{CV}^2(A), \tag{A.3}$$

where $\text{CV}(A)$ denotes the Coefficient of Variability of the random variable A .

Proof. Define $Y(\mathcal{P}_S(k))$ as

$$\begin{aligned} Y(\mathcal{P}_S(k)) &\triangleq \left[Q^{-1} \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} P_e^* \right) \right]^2 \\ &= \left[Q^{-1} \left(P_e^* + \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} - 1 \right) P_e^* \right) \right]^2. \end{aligned} \tag{A.4}$$

For $P_e^* \leq 10^{-8}$, $Y(\mathcal{P}_S(k))$ has the following Taylor expansion around P_e^* :

$$\begin{aligned} Y(\mathcal{P}_S(k)) &\cong [Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2 \\ &\quad + \frac{d[Q^{-1}(s)]^2}{ds} \Big|_{s=P_e^*} \left[\left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} - 1 \right) P_e^* \right] \\ &= [Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2 - 2 \left(\frac{a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S(k))}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle} - 1 \right), \end{aligned} \tag{A.5}$$

where to compute the above derivative we have used the fact that $Q(v)$ can be tightly approximated by $(1/\sqrt{2\pi}v)e^{-v^2/2}$, when $v^2 \gg 1$. Therefore $\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*)$ in expression (A.1) can be approximated by

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*) &= 4\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) Y(\mathcal{P}_S) \rangle \\ &\approx 4\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle \left[[Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 2 \left(\frac{\langle a^2(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle^2} - 1 \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

By using the above definition of $a(\gamma, k)$ as a random variable A

$$\frac{\langle a^2(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle}{\langle a(\gamma, \mathcal{P}_S) \rangle^2} - 1 = \text{CV}^2(A). \tag{A.6}$$

Now it follows immediately that whenever the inequality (A.3) holds, the optimal value of $\widehat{\text{SNR}}(P_e^*)$ reduces to expression (A.2). $\square$

Under the SOC conditions, the random variable A can only take values in the closed interval $[p_1 = a(\gamma, 0.05), p_2 = a(\gamma, 0.5)]$. On the other hand, it can be shown that the Coefficient of Variability $\text{CV}(A)$ of a random variable $A \in [p_1, p_2]$ is maximized (for large K) when its probability distribution is

$$Pr(\{k \in \Omega: A(k) = p_1\}) = \alpha \tag{A.7}$$

and

$$Pr(\{k \in \Omega: A(k) = p_2\}) = 1 - \alpha, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

with

$$\alpha = \frac{p_2}{p_2 + p_1}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

That is, when A is a binary random variable taking the boundary values p_1 and p_2 . In this case

$$CV(A) = \frac{p_2 - p_1}{2\sqrt{p_1 p_2}}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Under SOC we have that

$$\frac{[Q^{-1}(P_e^*)]^2}{2} \in [15.7, \infty) \quad (\text{A.11})$$

and, for all $\gamma \in [-1, 0]$, $CV^2(A)$ is upper bounded (worst case) between 0.8 ($\gamma = -1$) and 2.0 ($\gamma = 0$). Therefore, we conclude that under SOC, approximation (A.2) holds.

References

- [1] Korn I, Fonseka JP, Xing S. Optimal binary communication with nonequal probabilities. *IEEE Trans Commun* 2003;51: 1435–8.
- [2] Burrows M, Wheeler D. A block sorting lossless data compression algorithm. Research report 124. Digital Systems Center; 1994.
- [3] Wozencraft JM, Jacobs IW. Principles of communication engineering. New York: Wiley; 1965.
- [4] Ipatov V. Comments on optimal binary communication with nonequal probabilities. *IEEE Trans Commun* 2007;55:231.
- [5] Effros M, Visweswariah K, Kulkarni S, Verdú S. Universal lossless source coding with the burrows wheeler transform. *IEEE Trans Inf Theory* 2002;48:1061–81.
- [6] Balkenhol B, Kurtz S. Universal data compression based on the burrows wheeler transform: theory and practice. *IEEE Trans Comput* 2000;49:1–11.
- [7] Visweswariah K, Kulkarni S, Verdú S. Output distribution of the burrows wheeler transform. In: Proceedings of the IEEE international symposium on information theory. 2000. p. 53.
- [8] Caire G, Shamai S, Verdú S. Universal data compression using LDPC codes. In: Proceedings of the international symposium on turbo codes and related topics; 2003.
- [9] Caire G, Shamai S, Shokrollahi A, Verdú S. Fountain codes for lossless data compression. DIMACS series in discrete mathematics and theoretical computer science. American Mathematical Society; 2005.
- [10] Shamir GI, Wang L. Context decoding of low density parity check codes. In: Proceedings of the conference on information sciences and systems; 2005.
- [11] Xie K, Shamir GI. Context and denoising based decoding of non-systematic turbo codes for redundant data. In: Proceedings of the 2005 international symposium on information theory; 2005. pp. 1280–84.
- [12] Del Ser J, Crespo PM, Esnaola I, Garcia-Frias J. Source controlled turbo coding of sources with memory using the burrows wheeler transform. In: Fourth international symposium on turbo codes; 2006.
- [13] Rudin W. Real and complex analysis. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill; 1966.
- [14] Cover TM, Thomas JA. Elements of information theory. New York, NY: Wiley; 1991.
- [15] Shannon C. A mathematical theory of communication *Bell Systems Tech J* 1948;27:379–423, 623–56.

Pedro M. Crespo was born in Barcelona, Spain. In 1978, he received the engineering degree in Telecommunications from Universidad Politécnica de Barcelona. He received the M.Sc. in Applied Mathematics and Ph.D. in Electrical Engineering from the University of Southern California (USC), in 1983 and 1984, respectively. From September 1984 to April 1991, he was

a member of the technical staff in the Signal Processing Research group at Bell Communications Research, New Jersey, USA, where he worked in the areas of digital communication and signal processing. He actively contributed in the definition and development of the first prototypes of xDSL (digital subscriber lines transceivers). From May 1991 to August 1999 he was a district manager at Telefónica Investigación y Desarrollo, Madrid, Spain. From 1999 to 2002 he was the technical director of the Spanish telecommunication operator Jazztel. At present he is the director of the Electronics and Communications Department at the R&D center CEIT, San Sebastián, Spain. He is also a full professor at the Engineering School of the University of Navarra (TECNUN). Dr. Crespo is a Recipient of the Bell Communication Research Award of excellence. He holds seven patents in the areas of digital subscriber lines and wireless communications. His research interests include the general areas of digital communications, signal processing and information theory. Dr. Crespo is also a senior member of the IEEE.

Estíbaliz Loyo achieved her B.S. in Electrical Engineering in 2001 and her M.S. in Telecommunications Engineering in 2003 in ESIDE (Deusto University), where she achieved her preliminary defense developing several works on digital treatment over pathological speech signals. Currently she is a Ph.D. candidate of the Communication Systems and Mathematical Principles

of Information group at CEIT, where her research interests are focused on the applications of Fountain codes in several scenarios as deletion, insertion and substitution channels.

Javier Del Ser was born in Barakaldo, Spain, in 1979. After graduating with honors at the college *Nuestra Señora de Europa* in Getxo (Bizkaia, Spain), he joined the Faculty of Engineering (ETSI, www.ingeniaritza-bilbao.ehu.es) of the University of the Basque Country (Spain) to study Electrical Engineering, obtaining his combined B.S. and M.S. degree in May 2003. As a

member of the Signal and Communication Group at the Department of Electronics and Telecommunications at ETSI, he developed a signal processing system for the measurement of most power line supply quality parameters. After finishing this degree, he became a recipient of the *Fundación de Centros Tecnológicos Iñaki Goenaga* doctoral grant, which allowed him to start working towards his Ph.D. degree at Centro de Estudios e Investigaciones Técnicas de Gipuzkoa (CEIT), San Sebastián (Spain), in November 2003. In October 2006 he finally achieved the Ph.D. degree (*cum laude*) in Electrical Engineering.

In addition, from 2003 to 2005 he was a teaching assistant at TECNUN (University of Navarra, www.tecnun.es).

Currently he is an associate researcher at INTECOM core, and an associate professor of Data Transmission at TECNUN. His research interests are focused on communication and network information theory, factor graphs, joint source-channel coding, iterative decoding algorithms, and Turbo equalization schemes. Dr. Del Ser is listed in the both 2006 and 2007 edition of Who's Who in Science and Engineering, and is a member of both IEEE Communication and Signal Processing Societies.